

THE ASSOCIATION OF SELF-EFFICIENCY AND SELF-ESTEEM WITH SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF ATHLETIC AND NON-ATHLETIC ADOLESCENTS OF MALEKAN TOWN

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Abstract:

Social development is a continuous concept as are physical and psychological development which gradually evolves toward perfection. The objective of present study is to examine the association of self-efficiency and self-esteem with social development of male athletic and non-athletic adolescents. The statistical population of present study includes all male students of high schools in Malekan Town. The statistical sample is composed of 110 non-athletic students and 110 athletic students playing in group sports of volleyball, basketball, futsal, handball and football for more than four consecutive years with age range of 16 ± 1.5 years who are selected through random cluster sampling. The instruments of data collection in the present study are Weitzman's social development standard (1991), Coopersmith self-esteem inventory (1967). In addition, the measurement of self-efficiency is done through general self-efficacy scale (Sherer et.al, 1982). The results of present study show that self-esteem and self-efficiency have significantly positive association with social development.

Keywords: self-efficiency, self-esteem, social development, athletic, non-athletic

Introduction

The adolescence is a sensitive period in which an individual's emotions and thoughts are formed. In this age, the individuals learn the value and significance of regulations and social relationships and get prepare for social adjustment and development through complete observation of such rules [1]. Social development is actually the

development of social relationships of an individual so that he can adjust and adapt with the individuals in his society. Social development is the most significant aspect of essence of any person [2] and it includes a balanced set of social skills and adaptive behaviors that enables a person to have desired mutual relationships with other people, show positive reactions and refrain from behaviors with negative consequences. Some characteristics such as cooperation, responsibility, empathy, self-control and self-reliance are among the elements of social development [1].

Based on Weitzman's theory, social development is concurrent psychological and physical development which evolves into perfection. For majority of individuals, social development occurs gradually and naturally as a result of different experiences and it is commonly called "maturity". The social development in males has three stages of imitation, honoring one's character and social balance while it has four stages of obedience, anxiety, imitation and social balance for females. In the process of transition from the above stages, family, social groups and school are distinctively influential [4].

Garital et al [4] believe that physical activities such as group sports and extracurricular activities in the schools provides the conditions for social health and development because group sports activity provides numerous opportunities for social interactions, dealing with positive and negative stimuli and experiencing different psychological and physical conditions and as a result, the adolescents can consistently evaluate their abilities and psychological-physical capacities and abilities. The studies on this issue show different findings.

Farokhi and Seyed Zade [6] and Barrette [7] found out that there is no significant difference among the levels of social development of athletes playing individual sports, athletes playing group sports, and non-athletes. However, Karter and Toman [4] found out that the athletes of individual and group sports have higher social development than non-athletes. The results of their analyses showed the positive effect of physical activity on social development of adolescents. It should be noted that the benefits of physical activity is not limited to social development and it has certain effects on psychological and social characteristics of individuals. Self-esteem is one of the significant characteristics of human which is influenced by social interaction and physical activity. It is the feeling of value, confirmation, admission and value that a person feels about himself [8]. This personality trait is the result of social life and its values which represents itself in all daily activities of human and regarded as one of the most significant aspects of personality which determines one's behavioral characteristics. Self-esteem is influenced by internal and external factors. The internal factors refer to the ones that the person creates such as ideas, beliefs, actions, and behavior of an individual while external factors include environmental ones [9]. In

general, physical activity and exercise might create a feeling of efficiency and sufficiency in an individual and lead to increase of his self-esteem [10]. The other personality traits associated with social development and self-esteem which is influenced by physical activity is self-efficiency. Self-efficiency is associated with ability of an individual to effectively do his tasks and obtain verbal motivation from his successes and failures and witnessing the successes and failures of those who are similar to him. Therefore, it seems that persons with higher self-efficiency try more than those who have less self-efficiency. They work harder toward their goals and experience less fear [12].

In this regard, Marcos et al [12] and Blanchard et al [13] found out that there is a mutual association between physical activity and self-efficiency. Liang et.al [14] suggested that self-efficiency is directly associated with the level of physical activity. In other words, higher self-efficiency leads to more joy of physical activity. Due to significance of personality traits such as social development, self-esteem, self-efficiency, and their underlying factors in association with students as well as the paradoxical results regarding the association of physical activity with above characteristics and complexity of social relations in the contemporary societies, the necessity of dealing with social characteristics of students and the factors associated with them is felt more than ever. The increasing number of those who have problem in communicating with others and experience fear in their social interactions as wells the number of students with anxiety, depression, low self-esteem, and self-efficacy and social isolation justify the necessity of dealing with social development and personality factors (self-esteem and self-efficiency).

Methodology

The statistical population of present study included all male students of high schools in Malekan Town. The statistical sample was composed of 110 non-athletic students and 110 athletic students playing in group sports of volleyball, basketball, futsal, handball and football for more than four consecutive years with age range of 16 ± 1.5 years who were selected through random cluster sampling from the high schools of regions 2, 8, 9 and 11. The instruments of measuring social development of subjects was Weitzman's social development standard (1991). To measure the self-esteem of the subjects, the Coopersmith self-esteem inventory (1967) was used which included 35 items. In addition, the measurement of self-efficiency was done through general self-efficacy scale (Sherer et al, 1982). The descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used to describe data. In addition, inferential statistics such as Pearson correlation

coefficient was used to study the association among the personality traits of self-efficacy, self-esteem and social development among athletic and non-athletic students. In addition, multivariate regression was used to determine the prediction power of criterion variable (social development) by predictor variables (self-esteem and self-efficiency among athletic and non-athletic male students).

Results and Findings

The findings of Pearson correlation coefficient of social development with the variables of self-efficiency and self-esteem of athletic and non-athletic male students are shown in the following table.

Table 1: Pearson Correlation Coefficient of Social Development with Self-efficiency and Self-esteem of Athletic and Non-athletic Male Students

Subjects		Self- efficiency		Self-esteem	
		R	P	R	P
Male Athletes	Social Development	0.28	0.021*	0.26	0.008*
Male Non-athletes	Social Development	0.13	0.072	0.11	0.061

As the above table shows, the correlation between social development and self-efficiency for male athletic students is $r=0.28$ which shows its significance at the level of $P<0.05$. In addition, the correlation between social development and self-esteem for male athletic students is $r=0.26$ at the level of $P<0.05$ which shows its significance. But the correlation between self-efficiency and social development ($r=0.13$) and the correlation of self-esteem and social development ($r=0.11$) are not significant at the level of $P>0.05$. To determine multiple correlations of self-esteem and self-efficiency with social development among male athletic and non-athletic students, entry multiple regression was used. The association between self-efficiency and self-esteem as predictor variable and social development as criterion variable was analyzed for male athletic and non-athletic students. Based on the obtained results, the influence coefficients of the variable of self-efficiency ($B=0.056$ and $t=2.67$) and self-esteem ($B=0.039$ and $t=2.98$) show that the variable of self-efficiency with confidence of 99.01 percent ($P<0.009$) and the variable of self-esteem with confidence level of 99.06 percent ($P<0.004$) can predict the social development of male athletic students. This means that the increase of self-efficiency and self-esteem leads to increase of social development. Based on the obtained results, the influence coefficients of self-efficiency ($B=0.020$,

$t=1.085$) and self-esteem ($B=0.045$, $t=1.325$) show that each one of the variables of self-efficiency and self-esteem cannot predict social development among male non-athletic students.

Discussion and Conclusion

The results of present study showed that there is a significantly positive association between social development and the variables of self-esteem and self-efficiency among the male athletic students. The obtained results matches those of Carter and Tomsn [4]. As the stated, the physical activities in group sports not only provide the conditions for social development of students but also influence the development of social skills such as increase of self-confidence, self-esteem, self-control and belief in one's self-efficiency. Based on their viewpoint, the socialization of individuals through exercise means the alignment with group-based and social values and viewpoints. In this process, the students learn skills, knowledge and methods of social adjustment. They realize the possibility of mutual relationship as a result of consistent interactions. Payne and Isaacs found out that self-esteem and self-perception are among the most important characteristics of human influenced by the interaction of social development and physical activity. They stated that physical activity and social development are associated with each other and are regarded as influential factors upon psychological, physical, personal, and cultural development of an individual in his childhood and adolescence.

In addition, the results of multiple regression showed that the variable of self-efficiency with confidence level of 99.01 percent and the variable of self-esteem with confidence level of 99.06 percent have linear association with criterion variable among male athletic student and can predict social development in them but these variables lack the ability to explain social development among male non-athletic students. Bandura [11] suggested with the framework of his cognitive-social theory that high self-efficiency is essential for social development and association. This variable makes life more enjoyable for an individual and enables the person to cope with long-term pressures. Bandura stated that going through the way of social development demands a strong feeling of self-efficiency, self-confidence and self-esteem in an individual. In other words, one of the most significant issues regarding social development of individuals is creating a strong feeling of self-efficiency in them.

Based on the findings of present study and the previous ones, one could conclude that based on the role and significance of athletic activities, especial group sports activities, in social development of students, the education organization could

offer the conditions of doing group sports in school so as to enable their better social development and enhance their personality traits. The group sports activities help individuals to learn how to help other and cultivate their feelings of cooperation, tolerance, sacrifice, catching up with the group, independence and confidence, friendship with people and trusting them. As a result, motivating the students to do group sports due to enhancement of their social development and personality traits is one of the most significant duties of family, educational organizations, and educational centers. As Eliot and Maleki [15] believed, the students that face problems in developing their social skills often face the problems of learning, behavior complications, and low self-esteem and self-confidence. If this problem remains as it is, the person might face certain problems in long term such as cycle of failure, rejection by peers, poor education in school, adjustment problems in the community during adulthood.

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